

PERCEIVED INFLUENCE OF VALUES RE-ORIENTATION COUNSELLING ON NATIONAL SECURITY AND POLITICAL STABILITY AMONG YOUTHS IN KONTAGORA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF NIGER STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study investigated the perceived influence of values re-orientation counselling on national security and political stability among youths in Kontagora Local Government Area of Niger State. The research design adopted was descriptive survey. Using simple random sampling technique, 207 youths were sampled from various work sectors of Kontagora Local Government Area (Education, Finance, Judiciary Security and others). A 22 items questionnaire titled Values Re-Orientations for National Security and Political Stability Scale (VRNSPS) structured by the researcher with reliability coefficient of 0.86 was used. The data gathered was analyzed to answer the two research questions and test the two hypotheses formulated for the study. Descriptive statistical tool of mean was used to answer the research questions in the study while inferential statistical tool of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the formulated null hypotheses. The result obtained indicated that values re-orientation counselling would have influence on national security and political stability and that there is no significant difference in the perceived influence of values re-orientation counselling on national security ($F=.98, P=.42>.05$) and political stability ($F=.97, P=.43>.05$) on the basis of sector of the respondents. It was recommended among others that values re-orientation counselling should be provided in both formal and informal settings to help in re-educating the youth about the Nigeria national values.

Keywords: National security, political stability and values re-orientation counselling

Introduction

National security and political stability are unavoidable factors of national development. Security and instability are global issues; they are not peculiar to any nation of the world. The level of insecurity and instability may differ from one nation to the other. National security is the safekeeping of the nation as a whole. The priority of any nation is the protection of its territorial integrity, resources and citizen from internal and external attacks. It is a nation's military ability or the struggle to defeat internal and external aggression. A nation is secured once it is free from military threats or political coercion (Aliyu, 2012). According to Ordu and Owhonda (2019), national security is a strategy being put in place by a state or country to maintain peace and harmony as well as sovereignty. This informs the belief that national security is the preservation of independence and sovereignty of a nation or state. Ordu and Owhonda (2019) observed further that national security involves protecting citizens from anxiety and pervasive threats to their personal safety, physical wellbeing and core values. Otto and Ukpere (2012) stated that security must be related to the presence of peace, safety, happiness and the protection of human and physical resources or the absence of crisis, threats to human injury among others. Security threat differs from nation to nations. The major security

threat to Nigeria include poverty, electoral violence, Boko Haram, banditry, kidnapping, illegal arms importation, corruption, communal conflict and unemployment.

An insecure nation cannot develop effectively irrespective of its abundant wealth, commendable developmental goals, objectives, policies and programmes. It has been argued that an insecure environment impinges directly on development; it disenfranchises communities, contributes to poverty, distorts economies, creates instability and stunts political development. In Nigeria, apart from the millions of people who had been killed in course of one security breach or another, sources of livelihood were destroyed, families got disintegrated and social infrastructure were disrupted (Otto and Ukpere, 2012). Yahaya (2012) identified six elements of national security thus: Military security (capacity to defend itself and/or deter military aggression), political security (the stability of social order and the ability to maintain political stability and its sovereignty), economic security (ability to maintain, sustain and protect economic interests), food security (ability of a nation to feed its citizens without relying on importation), environmental security (ability to address environmental challenges e.g. earthquake, food drought) and health security (provision of health needs of citizens).

The absence of national security certainly leads to political instability. This is because citizens may be forced to engage the government and bring about frequent change in governance. According to Sottilotta, (2013) in Nomor, Lorember and Adamu, (2019), the concept of political stability is a very controversial concept. Sottilitta argued that, a first broad definition refers to the absence of domestic civil conflict and widespread violence. In this sense, a country can be considered rid of instability when no systematic attacks on persons or property take place within its boundaries; classic interpretation equates stability with government longevity; political stability draws on the lack of structural change, that is, the absence of internally or externally induced change in the basic configuration of a polity. Many factors may contribute to political instability in any nation. These factors include military incursion in governance, method of selecting leaders, electoral malpractices, unemployment, corruption, greediness and illiteracy.

Political stability has also been studied using six different measures: lack of violence, lack of structural change, lack of control, state functionality, indicators and correlations, and patterns of political behaviors (Margolis 2010, p. 327). This reduces investment and speed of economic development, increases the chances of government collapse and political unrest. Political instability has threatened national stability and security in the entire continent of Africa including Nigeria. The presence of national security and political stability could facilitate growth and development of a nation. The growth of any nation depends on its ability to be stable (security wise, politically and economically).

Youths have been described as important, able bodies and economically active group of the entire labour force of any nation. It is observed by Fan, Agu and Tsav (2016) that the energy, vigour, inventiveness, character and orientation of youth defined the rapidity of development and security of any society or nation. The United Nations considered individuals between the age group of 15-24 as youth. In Uganda, youth is from 12-30 years while in Nigeria it is between 18 and 35 years (National Youth Development Policy, 2001; Ibbih, Anthony & Itari, 2015). It is more of mere saying in Nigeria than reality, that youths are the leaders of tomorrow. Youths can only realize the goals of being leaders of tomorrow by maintaining national security and political stability with

consciousness of the national values and norms. This is because with insecurity, the youths are used as thugs and the life of many as future leaders are wasted.

The problem of insecurity and political instability in Nigeria is not lack of structure and strategies but neglect and abandonment of national values. The task of improving national security and political stability in a diversified nation like Nigeria will not only be difficult but almost impossible without a clear understanding and reorientation of the national values, hence values reorientation counselling is needed for youths. In Nigeria today, growth and advancement is being retarded in many aspects through outburst of materialistic tendencies of our youth. Nigerian youth rely so much on what is given to them during the electioneering process rather than what the community could benefit. It is beyond doubt that materialism has taken over government, political institutions, traditional and even religious institutions.

In the opinion of Njoku (2015), value implies acceptable standards, ideal way of doing things and living virtuous life in society. Value cannot function in socio-cultural vacuum since there is need for it to serve societal purposes. The Nigeria education as it is today is finding it difficult to inculcate the national values which Nigerian education is expected to promote in order to achieve the five main national objectives as stated in section 1 of the National Policy on Education. The national values include:

1. Respect for the worth and dignity of the individuals;
2. Faith in man's ability to make national decisions;
3. Moral and spiritual values in interpersonal and human relations;
4. Shared responsibility for the common good of the society;
5. Respect for the dignity of labour; and
6. Promotion of the emotional, physical and psychological health of all children.

According to Njoku (2015), the positive or dominant values that serve different societies along with Nigeria include respect and honour accorded to parents, elders, men and women of honour. Love and protection of the family and family name has been the practice in traditional and contemporary society of Nigeria. These national values are entrenched in the national identities including the national anthem, pledge and coat of arm. It is unfortunate that many school children are unconscious of these values as they were not consciously taught as the values which the nation upholds. The essence of the entrenchment of the values in these national identities is to educate every citizen concerning them and to uphold them in whichever part of the society one finds him or herself. In reality, if citizen can hold on to these values, the realization of the five national objectives of a free and democratic society; a just and egalitarian society; a united, strong and self-reliant nation; a great and dynamic economy; and a land of bright and full opportunities for all citizens as stated in the National Policy on Education will be easier. Hence, enhances the overall development of the nation.

Values reorientation counselling is very essential for youth personal development and upholding of national unity and growth. Values reorientation counselling is a type of counselling which helps in re-educating an individual on what are considered worthwhile and highly cherished by a group of individuals or a nation in order to live a worthy and satisfactory life in the society or nation where he or she lives. Njoku (2015) asserted that values re-orientation would lead to redemption and salvaging national characteristics and image. With value re-orientation Egwuatu (2013) in Oluwagbohunmi (2017) maintained

that Nigeria can be a better place and the system working effectively if Nigerians begin to have a change of mindset, get the right people and put them in leadership position. This mean that values re-orientation is restructuring and redirecting of people in the right direction. One of the benefits of values re-orientation according to Ukpabio, Ekere and Nnaji (2017) is the promotion of Nigerian democratic life and enhancement of safe and supportive environment. It is against this background that this paper investigated the perceived influence of values re-orientation counselling on national security and political stability among youths.

Statement of the Problem

National security and political stability are inevitable phenomena toward national development. An insecure nation cannot develop effectively irrespective of its abundant wealth, laudable developmental goals, objectives, policies and programmes. It has been argued that an insecure society interrupts directly on development; it disenfranchises communities, contributes to poverty, alters economies, creates instability and inhibits political development. In Nigeria, apart from the millions of people who had been killed in course of one security breach or another, sources of livelihood were destroyed, families got displaced and social infrastructure were disrupted. In Nigeria, the issue of insecurity such as banditry, armed robbery, kidnapping, assassination, raping have been reported. Farmers have been displaced by their activities.

The challenges of addressing these troubles is not lack of structure and strategies because government has put up measures in addressing these problems including the establishment and funding of several security agencies such as the Nigeria Police, State Security Service, Nigerian Armed Forces (Army, Navy and Air Force) and National Intelligence Agency. Despite these efforts, the rate of insecurity and instability is on the increase. Therefore, the researcher investigated the perceived influence of values re-orientation on national security and political stability among youths.

Research Questions

The following research questions are answered in the study:

1. What is the perceived influence of values re-orientation counselling in improving national security among youths in Kontagora Local Government Area of Niger State?
2. What is the perceived influence of value re-orientation counselling in improving political stability among youths in Kontagora Local Government Area of Niger State?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were tested in the study at 0.05 significant levels:

1. There is no significant difference in the perceived influence of values re-orientation counselling on national security among youth based on sector.
2. There is no significant difference in the perceived influence of values re-orientation counselling on political stability among youth based on sector.

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The study utilized simple random sampling technique to select 207 youths from the various work sectors of Kontagora Local Government Area (Education, Ministry, Banks and Security). To survey the perception of the respondent on the influence of values re-orientation counselling in improving national security and political stability, a 22 item questionnaire developed by the researcher titled Values Re-Orientation for National Security and Political Stability Scale (VRNSPS) was used. The questionnaire was given to three (3) experts in the field of counselling and test and measurement for face and content validation. The corrections, observations, suggestions and comments made by the experts were effected. Respondents were expected to respond to the questionnaire by indicating how strongly they agree or disagree with the items in the questionnaire. The questionnaire was pilot tested on 30 youths using split half method of reliability. The reliability coefficient of 0.86 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha.

To obtain data, an introductory letter was written by the researcher to the selected institutional authorities seeking their permission to carry out the study and the approval was granted. The researcher met the respondents and their consents led to the administration of the questionnaires. The questionnaires were administered and collected immediately. This made the researcher to get back all the administered questionnaires. The data gathered was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistical tool of mean was used to answer the research questions in the study while inferential statistical tool of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the formulated null hypotheses in the study.

Presentation of Results

This study investigated the perceived influence of values re-orientation on national security and political stability among youths. The results of the findings are presented thus:

Research Question One

What is the perceived influence of values re-orientation counselling in improving national security among youths?

To answer the research question, mean scores of 11 items on values and national security scale were used as presented in table 1.

Table 1: Mean rating of respondents on the perceived influence of values re-orientation counselling in improving national security among youths

SN	Values re-orientation counselling helps to improve national security by:	Mean	Remark
1	Re-awakening the youths' consciousness of what the nation stand to protect and defend	3.49	Agree
2	Making the youths realized that protection of the nation is a shared responsibility	3.51	Agree
3	Helping the youths understand, maintain and protect national interest	3.41	Agree

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4	Inculcating in the youths the consciousness to become useful members of the society that promotes tolerance and peaceful co-existence	3.27	Agree
5	Enabling youths to understand their environment and real life issues as it affects their lives and that of others.	3.39	Agree
6	Re-educating the youthson national values that will enable them build good human and harmonious relationships with others	3.57	Agree
7	Helping the youths acquire consciousness that will make them less aggressive and intolerable during crisis situation.	3.44	Agree
8	Equipping the youths with the knowledge and values that will bring about peace and tranquility	3.20	Agree
9	Enabling the youths acquire constructive peaceful means of solving problems	3.03	Agree
10	Enabling the youths develop non-violent conflict resolution attitude	3.29	Agree
11	Developing in youths the spirit of patriotism and commitment to the nation	3.46	Agree

Table 1 reveals that respondents agreed that values re-orientation counselling would have influence on national security. This is seen in the mean scores of 11 items (item 1 – 11) on the values scale with means scores above the mean average of 2.5.

Research Question Two

What is the perceived influence of value re-orientation counselling in improving political stability among youths?

Research question 2 was answered using the mean scores of 11 items on values and political stability scale which is presented in table 2.

Table 2: Mean rating of respondents on the perceived influence of values re-orientation counselling in improving political stability among youths

SN	Values re-orientation counselling for improving political stability	Mean	Remark
12	Allows them choose their leaders without fear base on national values	3.21	Agree
13	Allows them to rightly exercise their duty.	3.50	Agree
14	Enhances their political will and patriotism	3.38	Agree
15	Enhances sustainable democracy which involves their direct participation	3.40	Agree
16	Create the realization to change their deviant behaviours that could cause instability such as snatching of ballot boxes	3.43	Agree
17	Change their orientation about government must do everything for them.	3.30	Agree
18	Makes their ideas, attitudes and performance reflect the larger society.	3.34	Agree
19	Reduces their materialistic tendencies	1.96	Disagree
20	Enhances their own cultural and political development	2.27	Disagree
21	Makes them do the right thing in the right way in line with societal standard	2.60	Agree
22	Develops creative attitude in them	2.40	Disagree

Table 2 reveals that respondents agreed that values re-orientation counselling would have influence on political stability. Out of the 11 items (item 12 – 22) on the values scale, the respondents agree to 9 items with means scores above the mean average of 2.5. The respondents do not consider that values re-orientation counselling would influence political stability by helping to reduce materialistic tendency of the youths, enhance their cultural and political development and develop creative attitude in them.

Hypotheses Testing

Two research hypotheses were tested in this study at 0.05 significant level.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the perceived influence of values re-orientation counselling on national security among youth based on sector.

Table 3: Mean Summary of Respondents Based on Sector

SN	Variable	N	Mean
1	Education	96	36.98
2	Finance	19	37.16
3	Judiciary	23	37.87
4	Security	49	36.94
5	Others	20	36.65
	Total	207	

Table 4: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on Values Re-Orientation Counselling and Security Based on Sector

Sources of Variable	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	Df	Cal. f-ratio	Sig
Between Group	19.96	4.99	4		
Within Group	1026.46	5.08	202	0.98	.42
Total	1046.42		206		

P>.05

Table 4 shows that the p-value (0.42) is found to be greater than the chosen alpha of .05, hence the null hypothesis was accepted. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the perceived influence of values re-orientation counselling on national security among youth based on sector.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the perceived influence of values re-orientation counselling on political stability among youth based on sector.

Table 5: Mean Summary of Respondents Based on Sector

SN	Variable	N	Mean
1	Education	96	33.14
2	Finance	19	32.32
3	Judiciary	23	32.48
4	Security	49	32.65
5	Others	20	32.55
	Total	207	

Table 6: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on Values Re-Orientation Counselling and Political Stability Based on Sector

Sources of Variable	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	Df	Cal. f-ratio	Sig
Between Group	18.64	4.66	4		
Within Group	975.64	4.83	202	0.97	.43
Total	994.27		206		

P>.05

Table 6 reveals that the p-value (0.43) is greater than the chosen alpha of .05, therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference in the perceived influence of values re-orientation counselling on political stability among youth based on sector.

Discussion of Findings

Findings of the study revealed that values re-orientation counselling would have influence in improving national security. The respondents agreed that value re-orientation would reawaken youth consciousness about the nation, make them realize their responsibility in the development of the nation, develop in them the spirit of patriotism and commitment to the nation and re-educate the youths on national values that will enable them build good human and harmonious relationships with others. This buttress the assertion of Njoku (2015), that values re-orientation would lead to redemption and salvage national character and image. Egwuatu (2013) in Oluwagbohunmi (2017) maintained that Nigeria can be a better place and the system working effectively if it considers change in mindset, get the right people and put them in the right leadership position.

The findings also revealed that values re-orientation would have influence in improving political stability. The respondent believed that value re-orientation would enhance political will and patriotism which will allow right exercise of statutory duty and responsibility. This is in line with the findings of Orji and Umoren (2019), which revealed that values re-orientation helps in reminding individuals to detest laziness, embrace hard work, dignify labour, become good citizenship and being industrious. These are instruments of enhancing national security and political stability.

However, respondents disagree with the fact that values re-orientation can help in reducing materialistic tendency, enhancing personal cultural and political development and developing creativity. This disagreement may be due to the love or passion for wealth accumulation and corrupt practices that exist among Nigerians. This may prove the assertion of Ogude (2017) that the pursuit of material achievement over and above every other admirable virtue has become deep-rooted among all cadres of Nigerians. These are the cankerworms that have eaten deep into the hearts of our society. One of the benefit of value re-orientation according to Ukpabio *et al* (2017) is promoting Nigerian democratic way of life and enhance safe and supportive environment.

Sections of the respondents was found not to have significant difference in the perceived influence of values re-orientation counselling on national security and political stability. Respondents from different sector of the Kontagora Local Government of Niger State (education, finance, judiciary, security and others) differ not on the influence of values re-orientation on national security and political stability. All believed that values re-

orientation would help in repositioning the nation to meet the needs, aspirations and yearning of the citizens. This supports the position of Njoku (2015) that value re-orientation is repositioning Nigeria to where it ought to be in future.

Conclusion

No doubt that Nigerians are talented and skilled but the prevalence of insecurity and political instability in Nigeria has collapsed the developmental expectation of many Nigerians and deterred the development of the nation entirely. Without any contradiction, the present Nigeria is in dire need of value re-orientation. According to Olukogu (2011), “the emergence of a new Nigeria where peace, equity and justice will reign could only be realized when children are taught values needed to lead a righteous life”. Re-orientation of values becomes very important in the face of rising social problem such as corruption, kidnapping, banditry, indiscipline, raping and prostitution.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the researcher recommends as follows:

Many of the social vices prevalent in Nigeria are exhibited or perpetrated by youths and these youths are found in schools especially upper secondary and higher institution of learning. Value re-orientation counselling should be provided in all educational and non-educational institutions in both formal and informal setting to help in re-educating the youth about the Nigeria national values.

Government should introduce an effective reward and punishment system. Individual who demonstrated good value system should be selected for reward and vice versa. The application of this in schools, work places and political settings will encourage desirable behaviour and enhance hard work and patriotism which will foster security and stability of the nation

The National Orientation Agency Strategic Plan objective 2 is to promote Nigerian core values and positive attitudes through programmes of value re-orientation. This objective is not achievable if the agency is not adequately charged, monitored and funded. NOA should be well funded and charged to achieve this objective in order to increase awareness and national consciousness.

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